

FOCAL ADHESION KINASE EXPRESSION CORRELATES WITH NODAL METASTASIS IN PATIENTS WITH HEAD AND NECK CUTANEOUS SQUAMOUS CELL CARCINOMA

Pablo Munguía-Calzada MD¹, Iván Fernández-Vega MD PhD², Pablo Martínez-Cambor PhD^{3,4}, Susana Díaz-Coto⁵, Juana María García-Pedrero PhD⁶, Blanca Vivanco MD PhD², Cristina Galache Osuna MD PhD², Francisco Vazquez-Lopez MD PhD¹, Juan Pablo Rodrigo MD, PhD⁶, Jorge Santos-Juanes MD, PhD¹.

1. Service of Dermatology. Hospital Universitario Central de Asturias. Oviedo. Spain. Universidad de Oviedo.
2. Service of Pathology. Hospital Universitario Central de Asturias. Oviedo. Spain. Universidad de Oviedo.
3. Geisel School of Medicine at Dartmouth. Dartmouth College, Hannover, NH, USA.
4. Universidad Autónoma de Chile, Santiago, Chile.
5. Universidad de Oviedo. Spain
6. Department of Otolaryngology, Hospital Universitario Central de Asturias and Instituto de Investigación Sanitaria del Principado de Asturias. Instituto Universitario de Oncología del Principado de Asturias, University of Oviedo, Oviedo; CIBERONC, Spain.

Conflict of interest statement: The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

Funding sources: This work was funded by grants from the Plan Nacional de I+D+I 2013-2016 ISCIII (PI13/00259 to JMGP), PI16/00280 and CIBERONC (CB16/12/00390) Spain, and the FEDER Funding Program from the European Union.

Corresponding authors

Jorge Santos-Juanes MD, PhD.

Servicio de Dermatología

Hospital Universitario Central de Asturias

Avda Roma s/n, 33011 Oviedo, Spain

Email: jorgesantosjuanes@gmail.com

Juan Pablo Rodrigo, MD, PhD.

Servicio de Otorrinolaringología

Hospital Universitario Central de Asturias

Avda Roma s/n, 33011 Oviedo, Spain

Email: jprodrigo@uniovi.es

Running title: FAK in cSCC

Key words: focal adhesion kinase, Cortactin, cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma, prognosis, nodal metastasis.

Word count: Abstract: 148 words

Text: 2334words

Number of references: 40

Tables: 3

Figures: 2

ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: Focal adhesion kinase (FAK) and Cortactin overexpression is frequently detected in a variety of cancers, and has been associated with poor clinical outcome. However, there are no data in cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma (cSCC).

BACKGROUND: Focal adhesion kinase (FAK) and Cortactin overexpression is frequently detected in a variety of cancers and has been associated with poor clinical outcome.

OBJECTIVE: To investigate the relationship of FAK and Cortactin expression with the clinicopathologic features and the impact on the prognosis of cSCC patients.

METHODS: FAK and Cortactin expression was analyzed by immunohistochemistry on paraffin-embedded tissue samples from 100 patients with cSCC, and correlated with the clinical data.

RESULTS: FAK overexpression was a significant risk factor for nodal metastasis with crude and adjusted ratios (HRs) of 2.04, (95% CI (1.08-3.86), (p=0.029) and 2.23 (95% CI (1.01-4.91), (p=0.047), respectively. Cortactin expression was not a significant risk factor for nodal metastasis.

LIMITATIONS: Retrospective study limited to cSCC of the head and neck.

CONCLUSION: These findings demonstrate that FAK overexpression is an independent predictor of nodal metastasis that might be helpful for risk stratification and management of patients with cSCC.

INTRODUCTION

Cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma (cSCC) is the second most common malignancy of the skin after basal cell carcinomas, with an estimated annual incidence of 700,000 cases in the United States (1,2). There are high geographic and racial variations in the incidence of cSCC, ranging in Europa from 5-9 to 68-96 per 100,000 inhabitants to 291-499 per 100,000 in Australia (3).

Although basal cell carcinomas are the most common skin cancers, cutaneous SCC has greater metastatic potential. The exact incidence of metastases for cSCC is not truly known but is estimated to be around 2% to 5% (1). Given this low metastatic rate, most head and neck (HN) cSCC are not investigated or treated for occult metastases but rather treated based on positive clinical examination. Nevertheless, there are certain characteristics to a primary lesion that imply a higher risk of metastasis: primary lesion >2 cm in diameter; tumor thickness >6 mm; tumor on or around the ear; recurrent lesions; poorly differentiated grade; desmoplastic growth microvascular, lymphatic, or perineural invasion; advanced age; and a cSCC in an immunocompromised host (4,5). Even though the role of molecular factors in the lymphatic dissemination of cSCC has been studied; however, currently there are no clinically useful biomarkers of metastatic potential in primary cSCC (6) Coordinated regulation of the actin cytoskeleton is central to cell motility, invasion and metastasis. Focal adhesion kinase (FAK) and Cortactin are two proteins known to play central roles in actin regulation and/or participate in tumor motility in other cancers. These proteins may be equally important in cSCC and therefore should be good candidates for metastasis risk assessment of these patients (7-11).

Focal adhesion kinase (FAK) is a non-receptor tyrosine kinase that regulates diverse cellular functions, including adhesion, migration, invasion, polarity, proliferation and survival (11-15). Increased expression and/or activity of FAK in tumors has been

associated with more invasive and aggressive phenotypes (16,17). Consequently, FAK emerges as a key regulator of multiple biological processes that may have a major impact on the malignant phenotype (12,17), although the clinical significance of FAK expression in cSCC remains unexplored. FAK is encoded by the *FAK/PTK2* gene, located at 8q24; gains of this locus around *MYC* gene have been recurrently found in metastatic cSCCs (18), suggesting also its possible implication in the development of more aggressive phenotypes in this cancer type.

Cortactin is an actin-binding protein encoded by *CTTN* gene, located at 11q13 that regulates membrane dynamics, actin network assembly, cell-cell adhesion, invadopodia formation and matrix degradation, thereby promoting cell motility and invasion (19). Cortactin overexpression has been frequently and widely detected in multiple cancers, including head and neck squamous cell carcinoma, liver, breast, esophageal, ovarian, melanoma, gastric and colorectal cancer. Cortactin expression and/or gene amplification has been strongly associated with poor prognosis, and often found as an independent predictor of disease recurrence (20).

The overall goal of our study was to analyze FAK and Cortactin expression in a large series of patients with cSCC of the head and neck (cSCCHN), and to establish associations with clinicopathologic features and the possible impact on patient prognosis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Patients and procedures

The Department of Pathology electronic database at the Hospital Universitario Central de Asturias was searched to locate all the patients who had developed nodal metastases from cSCC of the head and neck (McSCCHN) between 1998 and 2008. All the electronic medical records were reviewed to determine whether outcomes of interest occurred.

Finally, a total of 50 primary cSCCHN who developed histologically confirmed lymph node metastasis were included. Controls (50 patients) were randomly selected among those patients with cSCCHN who did not develop any metastases and had a minimum follow-up of four years.

All the tumors were excised with conventional surgery. Patients with positive margins were excluded. None of the patients received any form of adjuvant therapy after their surgery. Ethics approval was obtained from the Hospital Universitario Central de Asturias Committee. Written informed consent was obtained from all patients. The Study was conducted, and the results were reported according to the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) guidelines for case-control studies. Clinical patient-related data were collected retrospectively. Patient age was defined as the age at the time of resection. Immunosuppressed patients included are chronic lymphatic leukemia (2), liver transplant (1), kidney transplant (5) heart transplant (1), diffuse large lymphoma B cell (1), and polycythemia vera treated with hydroxyurea (1).

Pathologic tumor staging based on the 7th AJCC classification was also registered (21). Outcome data were based on one tumor *per* patient.

Histopathologic evaluation

Each sample was analyzed and registered the following histopathologic features using hematoxylin-eosin (H&E) stained slides: maximum diameter, tumor thickness (dichotomized as ≤ 6 mm or > 6 mm; none lower than 2 mm), anatomic level (Clark's level), histopathologic degree of differentiation classified as well differentiated (1), moderately differentiated (2) and poorly differentiated (3), presence of desmoplasia, perineural or perivascular invasion, and the presence and number of tumor budding.

Tumor budding is defined as the presence of either isolated single cells or small cell clusters (≤ 4) scattered in the stroma ahead of the invasive tumor front. The intensity of tumor budding (budding index) was classified as low (< 5 buds) or high (≥ 5 buds) (22-24).

Tissue microarray (TMA) construction

Morphologically representative areas were selected from each individual tumor paraffin block for the construction of a TMA. Three 1 mm cylinders were taken to construct TMA blocks, as described previously (25). A total of four TMAs was created, containing three tissue cores from each of the 100 cSCCHN. In addition, each TMA included three cores of normal skin as an internal control.

Immunohistochemistry

The TMAs were cut into 3- μ m sections and dried on Flex IHC microscope slides (DakoCytomation, Glostrup, Denmark). The sections were deparaffinized with standard xylene and hydrated through graded alcohols into water. Antigen retrieval was performed heating the sections using Envision Flex Target Retrieval solution, high pH (Dako). Staining was done at room temperature on an automatic staining workstation (Dako Autostainer Plus) with mouse anti-cortactin monoclonal antibody Clone 30 (BD Biosciences Pharmingen, San Diego, CA) at 1:200 dilution, mouse anti-FAK monoclonal antibody Clone 4.47 (Upstate Biotechnology, Lake Placid, NY) at 1:250 dilution + Visualization System (Dako Autostainer). Counterstaining with hematoxylin was the final step.

Since Cortactin and FAK staining showed a homogeneous distribution, a semiquantitative scoring system based on staining intensity was applied, as previously

reported (25,26) (Figure 1a, 1b, 1c). Since normal skin showed negative expression of both proteins, scores were dichotomized as negative *versus* positive (weak, moderate and strong) expression.

Statistical analysis

Baseline demographic and clinical characteristics of the patients and pathological data were summarized with standard descriptive statistics. The primary endpoints were time to lymph-node metastasis and time to all-causes death, defined as the time from date of diagnosis of the primary tumor to date of diagnosis of metastasis or death for any cause, respectively. Tumor-specific deaths were also considered.

Conventionally, depending of their symmetry and nature, variables are described by using mean \pm standard deviation, medians with 25 and 75 percentiles or relative and absolute frequencies. The impact of the studied events on the considered cohort was summarized by incidence rates and 95% bootstrap confidence intervals.

Since the main studied outcome (i.e. presence of relapse) is not a final event and therefore potentially affected by competing risk-death without relapse is its competing event-, the cumulative incidence curves for relapsing were computed. The Gray estimator (27) was used to estimate them and they were compared from the procedure described therein. Then, proportional hazard regression models proposed by Fine and Gray (28) were used to compute the hazard ratios (HR) –used as average effect size measure- crude and adjusted by potential confounders. This procedure was also employed for computing the HRs for the tumor-specific death model. The 95% confidence intervals for the HRs were also reported.

The influence of the factors on mortality was analyzed by using standard proportional hazard Cox regression models. Crude and adjusted HRs and 95% confidence

intervals were provided. Adjusted models include variables related with severity of disease, buds and, additionally, the presence of relapse. This variable was included as time-dependent covariate.

Differences reporting p-values below 0.05 were considered statistically significant. All analyses were made by using the free environment R (www.r-project.org). Particularly, package survival and cmprsk were used.

RESULTS

One hundred white patients were enrolled in the study. Seventy-eight out of 100 patients were men (78%), and the mean age was 79 years (Table 1). FAK expression in at least more than 1% of tumor cells was observed in 69 cases (59%) (weak n=26; medium n= 24; strong n=19). Cortactin expression in at least more than 1% of tumor cells was detected in 64 cases (weak n=14; medium n=34; strong n=16) (Table 1) (64%). As illustrated in Figure 1, FAK and Cortactin expression had predominantly a homogeneous pattern in the tumor cells. We did not find a correlation between FAK and cortactin expression; the Spearman correlation coefficient between the FAK and Cortactin expression was 0.493 (CI95%, (0.317-0.653)).

Figure 2 shows the incidence per 100 patients/year (95% CI) in global data and by FAK levels. The incidence of metastasis is similar between none and weak expression (8.9% vs 8.3%) and medium and strong (22.4% vs 29.8%). Similar trends were observed for the specific death, but not for all causes mortality.

The mean age of patients with FAK-positive tumors (\pm standard deviation) was 79.35 \pm 6.43 years, and 78.97 \pm 6.43 years for the FAK-negative subgroup. The mean age of patients with Cortactin-positive tumors (\pm standard deviation) was 78.91 \pm 8.05 years, and 79.08 \pm 8.17 years for the Cortactin-negative subgroup.

In relation to the clinicopathologic features of cSCC patients, positive FAK expression was not significantly associated with any variable and negative Cortactin expression with perineural invasion; no other significant associations were observed (Table 2). It is worth to mention that a borderline association was observed between FAK expression and tumor thickness, which has been well-documented as strong predictor of nodal metastases. Thus, we found a 56.5% of cSCC >6 mm with positive FAK versus 35.5% of cSCC >6mm with negative FAK (p=0.053).

When analyzing the prognostic significance of FAK expression on univariate model, we found that FAK positive expression significantly predicted increased risk of nodal metastasis (HR=2.04, 95% CI 1.08-3.86; p = 0.029). This effect was modulated when adjusted by different potential confounders (Table 3). Furthermore, FAK expression was found a significant independent predictor in multivariate model (HR=2.23, 95% CI 1.01-4.91; p=0.047). Thickness, tumor horizontal size and tumor differentiation are the factors that showed a significant impact on metastasis, tumor mortality and all causes mortality. Potential confounding factors that could influence or contribute to tumor progression in our cohort study have been extensively discussed in Gonzalez-Guerrero et al (22). In contrast, Cortactin expression did not significantly predict the risk of nodal metastasis (Table 3). As illustrated in Figure 3 (*left panel*), a striking difference in nodal metastasis-free survival rates was observed between FAK-positive and FAK-negative patient subgroups (p=0.031). However, patients with FAK-positive tumors did not exhibit an increased risk of death compared to FAK-negative tumors (p=0.621). In marked contrast, no differences were observed between Cortactin-positive and Cortactin-negative patients in nodal metastasis-free survival rates (p=0.947 (*Figure 3, right panel*), nor in overall survival (p=0.863).

DISCUSSION

This study investigates for the first time the clinical significance of FAK and Cortactin expression as predictive factors for nodal metastases and survival in cSCC patients. We retrospectively analyzed FAK and Cortactin protein expression using a large homogeneous cohort of cSCCHN patients. These two proteins were prioritized for analysis based on their demonstrated role in tumor cell motility and invasion (29), and correlations with a more aggressive clinical course and nodal metastasis in other cancers (8,10).

We provide original evidence demonstrating that FAK-positive expression is an independent risk factor for nodal metastasis in cSCCHN patients. Similar results were obtained when performing the analysis from other points of view, considering a linear effect of the markers, non-clustered data, and other cut-off points for the protein expression (such as strong staining against others). The FAK studies published are based mainly on immunohistochemical with a negative versus positive approach and immunoblotting analysis (9,25,30).FAK expression has been rarely assessed in cSCC samples. FAK expression has been detected in premalignant intra-epithelial lesions and cSCC, but not in the perilesional skin (17) and it has been suggested that FAK plays an active role in cell proliferation. Nevertheless, its role as prognostic factor in cSCC has not yet been explored.

FAK overexpression and/or hyper-phosphorylation have been frequently detected in different cancer types, including head and neck, breast, colon, melanoma, thyroid, ovarian and hepatocellular carcinoma (31). However, most studies did not assess the correlations of FAK expression with the disease stage, patient outcome, or prognosis, except in hepatocellular carcinoma (15) and head and neck squamous cell carcinoma (10) where FAK expression has been associated with a worse outcome. Our findings are in good agreement to the so far reported data in these cancers.

In relation to overall survival, even though FAK-positive patients showed lower survival rates compared to the FAK-negative subgroup (multivariate model), these differences did not reach statistical significance. This may be related to the median age of our patients, which was very high. Alternatively, another possible explanation could be that the number of patients might be too small to obtain enough statistical power to detect significant associations. Nevertheless, the results of forest plot showed that FAK expression are very specific of disease.

Recently, it has been described that FAK inhibition increases immune surveillance in pancreatic adenocarcinoma (32). Noteworthy, this has quickly resulted in various clinical trials to test the FAK inhibitor defactinib and pembrolizumab (anti-PD-1) in advanced pancreatic cancer (clinicalTrials.gov NCT02546531) and defactinib and pembrolizumab in pancreatic cancer, non-small cell lung cancer, and mesothelioma (clinicalTrials.gov NCT02758587) (33). On the other hand, a recent study has demonstrated using a mouse model of cSCC that nuclear FAK regulates transcription of chemokines driving the recruitment of tumor-associated regulatory T cells, thus creating a tumor suppressive microenvironment by inhibiting cytotoxic CD8+ T cell activity (34). Together these data suggest that, in addition to the application of FAK as a biomarker for metastasis risk stratification in cSCC patients, is also emerges a promising therapeutic target also for cancer treatment.

Immunohistochemical analysis of Cortactin expression has thus far not been reported in cSCC. Cortactin overexpression has been found in multiple cancers, including head and neck squamous cell carcinoma (19), oral squamous cell carcinoma (35) lung squamous cell carcinoma, gliosarcoma, breast cancer, colorectal cancer and melanoma (36). Cortactin has been associated with tumor spreading and aggressive phenotypes, and suggested as a biomarker to predict metastasis (38). In marked contrast to these data,

Cortactin expression was not found to correlate with nodal metastasis in our cohort of cSCC patients and showed no impact on survival. Nevertheless, our findings are in good agreement with those reported by Sato et al in Head and neck squamous cell carcinoma (39).

We are aware that there are several limitations in our work. First, there are potential biases due to its retrospective nature. Second, the study is limited to cSCCHN. Third, these findings are based on patients treated in a University Hospital; hence the percentage of poor prognostic tumors might be higher due to referral than in the daily ambulatory practice. Fourth, the study was performed in a single institution. Fifth, immunohistochemical analysis was carried out using tissue microarrays; however, FAK and Cortactin expression pattern was quite homogeneous and concordant in the three representative tissue cores selected from each tumor. In conclusion, this study unveils the independent prognostic relevance of FAK expression using a large homogeneous cohort of cSCCHN patients. The herein presented data reveal that FAK expression is a significant independent predictor for the risk of nodal metastasis in cSCCHN patients. Nevertheless, these results require validation in prospective studies also including cSCC from other sites to further confirm the potential of FAK expression as a useful biomarker for risk stratification. Ultimately, this could also provide the rationale for the use of molecular therapies targeting FAK in inoperable or metastatic cSCC, since FAK inhibitors have emerged as a promising therapeutic strategy (32,39,40) and are currently being evaluated in various clinical trials in cancer patients.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We thank Aitana Vallina and Eva Allonca for excellent technical assistance.

REFERENCES

1. Karia PS, Han J, Schmults CD. Cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma: estimated incidence of disease, nodal metastasis, and death from disease in the United States, 2012. *J Am Acad Dermatol*. 2013;68:957-966.
2. Rogers HW, Weinstock MA, Harris AR, et al. Incidence estimate of nonmelanoma skin cancer in the United States, 2006. *Arch Dermatol*. 2010; 146:283-287.
3. Keena ST, Zwald FO, Schmults CD. Cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma. Que SKT, Zwald FO, Schmults CD. *J Am Acad Dermatol* 2018;78:237-247.
4. Thompson AK, Kelley BF, Prokop LJ, Murad MH, Baum CL. Risk Factors for Cutaneous Squamous Cell Carcinoma Recurrence, Metastasis, and Disease-Specific Death: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *JAMA Dermatol*. 2016;152:419-428.
5. Eigentler TK, Leiter U, Häfner HM, Garbe, Röcken M, Breuninger H. Survival of Patients with Cutaneous Squamous Cell Carcinoma: Results of a Prospective Cohort Study. *J Invest Dermatol*. 2017;137:2309-2315.
6. Ashford BG, Clark J, Gupta R, Iyer NG, Yu B, Ranson M. Reviewing the genetic alterations in high-risk cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma: A search for prognostic markers and therapeutic targets. *Head Neck*. 2017;39:1462-1469.
7. Clark ES, Whigham AS, Yarbrough WG, Weaver AM. Cortactin is an essential regulator of matrix metalloproteinase secretion and extracellular matrix degradation in invadopodia. *Cancer Res* 2007;67:4227-4235.
8. Rodrigo JP, García-Carracedo D, García LA, et al. Distinctive clinicopathological associations of amplification of the cortactin gene at 11q13 in head and neck squamous cell carcinomas. *J Pathol* 2009;217:5123–5165.
9. McLean GW, Carragher NO, Avizienyte E, et al. The role of focal-adhesion kinase in cancer - a new therapeutic opportunity. *Nat Rev Cancer* 2005;5:505-515.
10. Canel M, Secades P, Garzón-Arango M, et al. Involvement of focal adhesion kinase in cellular invasion of head and neck squamous cell carcinomas via regulation of MMP-2 expression. *Br J Cancer* 2008;98:1274-1284.
11. Kleinschmidt EG, Schlaepfer DD. Focal adhesion kinase signaling in unexpected places. *Curr Opin Cell Biol* 2017;45:24-30.
12. Serrels A, McLeod K, Canel M, et al. The role of focal adhesion kinase catalytic activity on the proliferation and migration of squamous cell carcinoma cells. *Int J Cancer*. 2012;131:287-97.

13. Frame MC, Patel H, Serrels B, Lietha D, Eck MJ. The FERM domain organizing the structure and function of FAK. *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol* 2010;11:802-14.
14. Canel M, Byron A, Sims AH, et al. Nuclear FAK and Runx1 Cooperate to Regulate IGFBP3, Cell-Cycle Progression, and Tumor Growth. *Cancer Res.* 2017;77:5301-5312.
15. Panera N, Crudele A, Romito I, Gnani D, Alisi A. Focal Adhesion Kinase: Insight into Molecular Roles and Functions in Hepatocellular Carcinoma. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2017;5:18. pii: E99.
16. Chatzizacharias NA, Giaginis C, Gatzidou E, et al. Expression and clinical significance of FAK and Src proteins in human endometrial adenocarcinoma. *Pathol Oncol Res.* 2011;17:277-285.
17. Choi CW, Kim YH, Sohn JH, Lee H, Kim WS. Focal adhesion kinase and Src expression in premalignant and malignant skin lesions. *Exp Dermatol* 2015; 24:361-364.
18. Li YY, Hanna GJ, Laga AC, Hadad RI, Lorch JH, Hammerman PS. Genomic analysis of metastatic cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma. *Clin Cancer Res.* 2015;21:1447-1456.
19. Rothschild BL, Shim AH, Ammer AG, et al. Cortactin overexpression regulates actin-related protein 2/3 complex activity, motility, and invasion in carcinomas with chromosome 11q13 amplification. *Cancer Res* 2006;66:8017-8025.
20. Kirkbride KC, Sung BH, Sinha S, Weaver AM. Cortactin: a multifunctional regulator of cellular invasiveness. *Cell Adh Migr* 2011;5:187-198.
21. Edge SB, ed, Byrd DR, ed, Compton CC, ed, Fritz AG, ed, Greene FL, ed, Trotti A III, ed. American Joint Committee on Cancer Cancer Staging Manual. 7th ed. New York, NY: NYL Springer;2010.
22. Gonzalez-Guerrero M, Martínez-Cambor P, Vivanco B, et al. The adverse prognostic effect of tumor budding on the evolution of cutaneous head and neck squamous cell carcinoma. *J Am Acad Dermatol.* 2017;76:1139-1145.
23. Karayannopoulou G, Euvrard S, Kanitakis J. Tumour Budding Correlates with Aggressiveness of Cutaneous Squamous-cell Carcinoma. *Anticancer Res.* 2016;36:4781-4785.
24. Fujimoto M, Yamamoto Y, Matsuzaki I, et al. Tumor budding is an independent risk factor for lymph node metastasis in cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma: a single center retrospective study. *J Cutan Pathol.* 2016;43:766-771.
25. Menéndez ST, Rodrigo JP, Alvarez-Teijeiro S, et al. Role of HERG1 potassium channel in both malignant transformation and disease progression in head and neck carcinomas. *Mod Pathol* 2012;25:1069-1078.

26. Rodrigo JP, Alvarez-Alija G, Menéndez ST, et al. Cortactin and focal adhesion kinase as predictors of cancer risk in patients with laryngeal premalignancy. *Cancer Prev Res (Phila)* 2011;4:1333-1341.
27. Gray RJ. A class of K-sample tests for comparing the cumulative incidence of a competing risk. *Annals of Statistics* 1998;16:1141-1154.
28. Fine, J., Gray, R. A proportional hazards model for the subdistribution of a competing risk. *Journal of the American Statistical Association* 1999;94:496-509.
29. Kelley LC, Shahab S, Weed SA. Actin cytoskeletal mediators of motility and invasion amplified and overexpressed in head and neck cancer. *Clin Exp Metastasis* 2008;25:289-304.
30. Villaronga MA, Hermida-Prado F, Granda-Díaz R, et al. *Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev* 2018; 27:805-813.
31. Golubovskaya, V.M. Targeting FAK in human cancer: From finding to first clinical trials. *Front. Biosci.* 2014; 19, 687–706.
32. Jiang H, Hegde S, Knolhoff BL, et al. Targeting focal adhesion kinase renders pancreatic cancers responsive to checkpoint immunotherapy. *Nat Med.* 2016;22:851-860.
33. Symeonides SN, Anderton SM, Serrels A. FAK-inhibition opens the door to checkpoint immunotherapy in Pancreatic Cancer. *J Immunother Cancer.* 2017;21:5-17.
34. Serrels A, Lund T, Serrels B, et al. Nuclear FAK controls chemokine transcription, Tregs, and evasion of anti-tumor immunity. *Cell.* 2015;163:160-173.
35. Noorlag R, Boeve K, Witjes MJ, et al. Amplification and protein overexpression of cyclin D1: Predictor of occult nodal metastasis in early oral cancer. *Head Neck.* 2017;39:326-333.
36. MacGrath SM, Koleske AJ. Cortactin in cell migration and cancer at a glance. *J Cell Sci* 2012;125:1621-1626.
37. Zhang X, Liu K, Zhang T, et al. Cortactin promotes colorectal cancer cell proliferation by activating the EGFR-MAPK pathway. *Oncotarget.* 2017;8:1541-1554.
38. Sato H, Hatanaka KC, Hatanaka Y, et al. High level expression of AMAP1 protein correlates with poor prognosis and survival after surgery of head and neck squamous cell carcinoma patients. *Cell Commun Signal* 2014;12:12-17.
39. Sulzmaier FJ, Jean C, Schlaepfer DD. FAK in cancer: Mechanistic findings and clinical applications. *Nat Rev Cancer* 2014;14:598-610.
40. Serrels A, Frame MC. FAK goes nuclear to control antitumor immunity-a new target in cancer immuno-therapy. *Oncoimmunology* 2016;5: e1119356.

FIGURES

Figure 1: Immunohistochemical analysis of cortactin and FAK expression in cSCC tissue specimens ($\times 20$). A, cortactin: weak; B, cortactin: moderate; C, cortactin: strong; D, FAK: weak; E, FAK: medium; F, FAK: strong

Figure 2: Incidence rate per 100 patients/year and 95% confidence interval for Metastasis, Death and Specific-Death for the whole cohort and by FAK levels

Figure 3: Fine gray estimates of nodal metastasis after resection of the cSCC on FAK-positive versus FAK-negative subgroups (left), and on cortactinpositive versus cortactin-negative subgroups (right).

TABLES

Table 1. FAK and cortactin expression in cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma of Head and Neck (SCCHN) and metastatic cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma of Head and Neck (McSCCHN).

FAK	None	Weak	Medium	Strong	p-value
cSCCHN	20 (40%)	17 (34%)	8 (16%)	5 (10%)	0.007
McSCCHN	11 (22%)	9 (18%)	16 (32%)	14 (28%)	
Cortactin					
cSCCHN	19 (38%)	10 (20%)	16 (32%)	5 (10%)	0.168
McSCCHN	17 (34%)	4 (8%)	18 (36%)	11 (22%)	

Table 2. Association between FAK and Cortactin expression and clinicopathologic features of patients with primary cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma.

	Global N=100	FAK expression			Cortactin expression		
		None N= 31	Others N=69	p-value	None N= 36	Others N=64	p-value
Sex, MALE	78	27 (87.1%)	51 (73.9%)	0.111	29 (80.6%)	49 (76.6%)	0.422
Age, Mean±sd	79.0 ± 8.1	79.3 ± 6.4	78.8 ± 8.7	0.722	79.1 ± 8.2	78.9 ± 8.1	0.917
Tumor thickness, mm							
Mean±sd	8.95 ± 6.56	7.39 ± 5.55	9.65 ± 6.89	0.085	10.11 ± 7.71	8.30 ± 5.78	0.224
>6mm	50	11 (35.5%)	39 (56.5%)	0.053	19 (52.8%)	31 (48.4%)	0.418
Anatomic Level, ≥4	75	21 (67.7%)	54 (78.3%)	0.190	28 (77.8%)	47 (73.4%)	0.409
Tumor horizontal size							
Mean±sd, mm	22.6 ± 14.2	21.3 ± 11.8	23.3 ± 15.2	0.477	25.6 ± 17.5	20.8 ± 11.7	0.122
>20mm	35	12 (38.7%)	23 (33.3%)	0.381	16 (44.4%)	19 (29.7%)	0.103
Tumor differ, 1-2	96	30 (96.8%)	66 (95.7%)	0.635	34 (94.4%)	62 (96.9%)	0.455
Desmoplastic growth	14	5 (16.1%)	9 (13.0%)	0.449	6 (16.7%)	8 (12.5%)	0.384
Tumor site, Ear	36	12 (38.7%)	24 (34.8%)	0.436	13 (36.1%)	23 (25.9%)	0.577
TNM, pT2=2	86	25 (80.6%)	61 (88.4%)	0.231	30 (83.3%)	56 (87.5%)	0.384
Inflammation				0.820			0.067
0	25	9 (29.0%)	16 (23.2%)		13 (36.1%)	12 (18.8%)	
1	61	18 (58.1%)	43 (62.3%)		21 (58.3%)	40 (62.5%)	
2	14	4 (12.9%)	10 (14.5%)		2 (5.6%)	12 (18.8%)	
Other SCC,	29	9 (29.0%)	20 (29.0%)	0.587	9 (25.0%)	20 (31.3%)	0.336
Immunosup,	11	3 (9.7%)	8 (11.6%)	0.539	5 (13.9%)	6 (9.4%)	0.352
Perineural invasion,	14	5 (16.7%)	9 (13.2%)	0.435	9 (35.7%)	5 (7.9%)	0.019
Lymph-Vasc. Invas.	4	1 (3.2%)	3 (4.3%)	0.635	2 (5.6%)	2 (3.1%)	0.455
Tumor buds, >0	45	11 (35.5%)	34 (49.3%)	0.143	20 (55.6%)	25 (39.1%)	0.084
Tumor buds, >5	20	4 (12.9%)	6 (23.2%)	0.180	7 (19.4%)	13 (20.3%)	0.568

Tumor differentiated; 1: well differentiated; 2: moderately differentiated. Inflammation; 0: none; 1: mild; 2: strong.

Table 3. Univariate and multivariate model for the effect of FAK and Cortactin expression on nodal metastasis and overall survival.

FAK expression	Metastasis		Tumoral Mortality		All-causes Mortality	
	HR (95% CI)	p-value	HR (95% CI)	p-value	HR (95% CI)	p-value
Univariate	2.04 (1.08-3.86)	0.029	1.55 (0.76-3.14)	0.230	0.92 (0.56-1.50)	0.731
Multivariate	2.23 (1.01-4.91)	0.047	1.40 (0.53-3.70)	0.500	1.05 (0.62-1.77)	0.848
Age	1.00 (0.97-1.04)	0.820	1.03 (0.99-1.08)	0.170	1.08 (1.04-1.12)	<0.001
Gender	0.81 (0.33-1.95)	0.640	0.55 (0.22-1.36)	0.190	0.57 (0.30-1.07)	0.082
Thickness	3.05 (1.40-6.65)	0.005	3.95 (1.61-9.71)	0.003	1.32 (0.71-2.47)	0.384
Tumor horizontal size	3.03 (1.50-6.12)	0.002	2.71 (1.24-5.92)	0.012	2.73 (1.41-5.30)	0.003
Tumor differentiation	0.43 (0.23-0.80)	0.008	0.29 (0.13-0.64)	0.002	0.39 (0.22-0.68)	0.001
Cortactin expression						
Univariate	1.02 (0.56-1.85)	0.950	0.99 (0.51-1.91)	0.970	0.74 (0.46-1.20)	0.225
Multivariate	0.90 (0.49-1.67)	0.740	0.88 (0.43-1.81)	0.730	0.75 (0.46-1.23)	0.248
Age	1.00 (0.96-1.04)	1.000	1.03 (0.98-1.09)	0.220	1.09 (1.04-1.13)	<0.001
Gender	0.72 (0.34-1.52)	0.380	0.51 (0.22-1.19)	0.120	0.53 (0.29-0.99)	0.046
Thickness	4.10 (1.90-8.82)	<0.001	4.60 (1.96-10.77)	0.004	1.57 (0.84-2.92)	0.151
Tumor horizontal size	2.26 (1.15-4.43)	0.018	2.37 (1.07-5.26)	0.033	2.36 (1.25-4.45)	0.008
Tumor differentiation	0.43 (0.23-0.81)	0.010	0.30 (0.13-0.66)	0.003	0.39 (0.22-0.68)	0.001